

Synonyms generation based on Deep learning models.

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1. Introduction

When using modern search engines or indexer engines, users have to formulate their queries in natural language and in free format. The search engines we talk about here are worldwide used systems like Google and also software tools like Elasticsearch, Solr and others. Worldwide search engines are used to query corpora managing general topics documents. But engines like Elasticsearch and Solr are used to query corpora managing documents in a specific domain.

In a Big data context application, documents are created outside the company. And the user does not have an idea about the exact terms used. So when submitting his query, May be he did not use the same words used by document authors. In this case the solution found since many years is using thesaurus. Thesauri are kind of dictionaries describing some ontology using much type of relations between words or terms. We could site some: generic term, specific term, preferred term and so on. Those dictionaries (thesauri) are created manually. Is it possible to use them in the context when the corpora are not huge and documents are created inside the company?

In the era of internet, cloud and big data this tool could not be used. And, in general, search engines include such capability by adding a function allowing the use of what is called synonyms file. Elasticsearch for example implement this functionality within analyzers. In synonym file we could use many type of relations like abbreviations, acronyms, homonyms etc.

The big issue is how to create this file? It is a hard work to create it manually. So our idea is to produce this file automatically. The last progress research in deep Learning technology could be a good solution. More precisely, word embedding algorithms are suitable to generate synonyms. There is a variety of algorithms or methods, the most famous are: Word2vec, GloVe and FastText. They are implemented in many deep Learning systems like TensorFlow, Caffe etc. In case of using multi-domain corpora we used pre-trained and open models provided by Google (model trained on Google News), Stanford (model trained on specific corpora), and Facebook (model trained on Wikipedia).

Having those models downloaded, we developed a program that generates a file where each line contains a list of comma separated words; each line represents a cluster of words having closer similarity. This file will be used by search engine to reformulate the query.

In the other side, when using a specific domain corpora (finance, banking, insurance, transport etc), we have to create and train a specific model using the same embedding

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algorithms and methods. After that we use the same program to enrich the synonym file.
To easily put in place this system we are using Gensim, Keras and SpaCy.

2. Aim

Our main goal is to generate synonyms to be used with search engines.

3. Material and methods

To achieve this work, we download, from web sites, some of most free approved Deep learning models from Google, Stanford, and Facebook. Those pre-trained models are created using word embedding technics. In order to generate clusters of synonym words we some open frameworks like Keras, Gensim and SpaCy.

4. Results

Many synonym files and clusters are created from the most famous models in the Deep learning area in Natural Language Processing.

5. Conclusions

Here we demonstrate and present a method which is easy and more cost-effectively to deploy and use Deep learning algorithms and methods to automatically generate synonyms.

6. Keywords

Deep learning, Natural Language Processing, Word Embedding, Gensim, SpaCy, Keras, Synonym, Search engines

Author biography

Nabil FEGAIERE is a Big Data & Data Science expert. As Big Data architect and trainer, since 2012, he worked in many Big Data projects for some French companies Like Banque de France, Orange, But, LA POSTE, EDF, AMUNDI, Pôle Emploi.

He Also participated and participating as a speaker in international conferences (Salon Big Data Paris in 2016, Data Science and Big Data Analytics 2018 - Toronto, Computer Science and Cloud Computing 2018 – Barcelona, IHEC Summer School 2018- Tunis-Tunisia).

From 1997 to 2011, Nabil worked as Data Engineering Expert for many companies: Société Générale, BNP Paribas, Cegetel, Tomson, Sanofi.

At the same time he was working, from 2003 to 2007, as a professor and Head of Computer Science Department at University of science Gafsa where he directed many projects in the domain of Natural Language Processing.

From 1992 until 1996, Nabil worked as a Natural Language Processing scientific researcher in the “Institut du Monde Arabe” in Paris. Where he experimented many applications in

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Nabil holds a PhD in computer Science from University of Paris 11 in France and a Master degree of Computer Science from ISG Tunis in Tunisia. He also holds many professional certificates from international companies